

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE SCHOOLS OF MIRACULOUS PAINTING (MINIATURE) OF THE EAST OF THE PERIOD OF RENAISSANCE TODAY

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Abstract. *The contributions of great painters, poets and painters were incomparable in the flourishing of wonderful painting in close connection with the art of literature. The Renaissance period is the achievement of the Eastern miraculous painting schools to this level, the perfection of the compositional solution of the created works, the delicacy of the lines and the uniqueness of working with paint. Anyone who sees such elegant and unique works will be moved by the heart and will be the reason for the love of fine art.*

Keywords: *wonderful painting, painter, miniature, composition, element, book art, portrait, still life, sketch, hermitage, balance.*

Introduction. In visual arts, the miracle flourished in close connection with painting, miniature, and book art. As a result of this, in Iran (Tabriz), India, Herat, Bukhara, Samarkand, Turk, Movoraunnahr, Azerbaijan, and many other regions, wonderful painting schools began to appear. Many painters, such as Mirak Naqqosh, Kamoliddin Behzod, Kasim Ali, Ustad Gung, Abdullah ibn Fazil, Aga Miraq, Kesu, Ustad Shamsiddin, Ja'far from Samarkand, Abdul Baki Tabrizi worked in these schools.

Tabriz school of miraculous painting was established in Tabriz city (Iran) at the beginning of the 14th century. In 1522, Shah Ismail appointed Kamoliddin Behzod as the head of this school. After that, the combination of local artistic traditions and the traditions of Herat led to further development of this art.

Painters such as Sultan Muhammad, Qasim Ali, Mirsaid Ali, Muzaffar Ali, Mirza Ali enriched the works of Alisher Navoi, Nizami Ganjavi, Jami with beautiful and charming paintings.

As a representative of the Tabriz school, Musavvir Qasim Ali created the work "Alshper Navoi and Sultan Muhammad Mirza" and went down in history through this work.

Indian painting school is divided into Gujarati, Rajnut, Baburi schools. In contrast to these schools, the school of the Baburis developed widely. It was mainly developed in the second half of the 15th century and in the 18th century under the influence of Iranian and Central Asian painting. The activities of these schools are closely related to the works of famous painters Mir Syed Ali and Abdusamad of Shiraz.

It is reflected in the book "Boburnoma", which is considered a bright example of the Boburi school, which is currently kept in the Museum of Oriental Art in Moscow. Kamoliddin Behzod, Shah Muzaffar, Boysunqur Mirza and other artists contributed greatly to the decoration of "Boburnoma" with paintings and patterns.

The Indian school of painting was invented in the 16th century and was founded by Babur and Khumayun, but the painters who greatly contributed to its development are Mir Syed Ali, Abdusamad Sherozi, Basova, Dust Devona, Disvinta, and Farrukhbek.

The great artists of their time, Mir Syed Ali, were awarded the title of "Nadir-ul Mulki Humayun", Abdusamad Shirozi was awarded the title of "Shirin Kalam", and Ustad Mansur was awarded the honorary title of "Nadir-ul Asr". In addition to this, Lal, Mukund, Madku, Djanu, Jagan, Mahesh, Tara, Miskina, Sanwada also left history with their unique contribution to the development of Indian painting.

(Afghanistan) Herat Mujaz Painting School. This trend arose in Herat in the 15th century due to the increase in demand for elegant handwritten books and flourished in its time. In the 2nd quarter of the Middle Ages, this type of art flourished after the arrival of painters such as Syed Ahmed, Khoja Ali, and Ja'far Tabrizi from Samarkand. Such development was greatly influenced by statesmen such as Husayn Boygaro, Alisher Navoi, Shahrukh, Gavharshokh, Boysunkur Mirza.

We can list Kamoliddin Behzod, Maulana Khalil Mirza, Shahrukhdy, Mirak Naqqosh, Khuja Muhammad, Muzaffar as major representatives of the Herat school of painting.

The paintings of Saadi's "Gulistan" (1427), Navoi's "Khamsa" (1431), Firdawsi's "Shahnama" (1424-1431) are among the best works of the Herat school. These works are kept in the Hermitage Museum in St. Petersburg, Gulistan Palaces in Tehran. Nizami's miniature paintings such as "Khamsa" worked in cooperation with the great representatives of the miniature school, Kamoliddin Behzod, Khuja Mohammad Naqqosh, Muzaffar, painter Qasim Ali, are located in the British Museum in London.

As we know, the miniature schools of Central Asia and India flourished and flourished under the influence of Herat's wonderful school of painting.

Azerbaijan miraculous school of painting. Tabriz painting within Azerbaijan was founded, and this school rose to a high level of development, especially in the 14th and 16th centuries.

One of the famous painters who lived and worked in Tabriz during this period is Pir Syed Ahmed Tabrizi, according to some reports, he was a teacher of Kamoliddin Behzad, and learned the secrets of art from Behzad's teacher Tabrizi.

Literature, art and culture flourished during the reign of Shah Ismail, the founder of the Safavid dynasty. Among the created masterpieces, we can take as an example pictures of Abdulkasim Firdavsi's "Shahnama", "Bo'ston" by Saadi Shirozi, and "Hamsa" by Nizami Ganjavi.

The most developed period of the Turkish mujaz painting school dates back to the 15th century. According to the decree of Sultan Mahmud II, many painters and poets gathered in the palace. According to sources, there were Iranians, Arabs, Circassians, Mojar, and Moldovans among the participants. According to some documents, in 1425, 29 painters and engravers created works in the painting workshop of the palace, and the "Fotix album" and "Istanbul albums" compiled by them were famous in their time.

Among them, many painters and painters, such as Baba Naqqosh, Sheikh Mustafa, Abdulghani, Agha Mirak, Sheikh Kamani, Shahquli, Jalalzada Mustafa, who came from Central Asia and Khorasan, worked in the court of the Turkish sultan.

Nigori's "Portrait of Sultan Suleiman I", portraits of Sultan Salim II, "Sultan and his followers" by Jalalzada Mustafa, "Portrait of Khusrav and Sultan Salim II" by Osman, "Ertakchi", "Kiziqchi", "Portrait of La'linqaba" and many other similar works are among the classic examples in terms of their high artistic level and quality.

Lighting, spatial qualities, charm of colors in the image, the ability to describe each element delicately and artistically in the above-mentioned works, all of this affects the viewer's heart, gives

